

ImproRisk

“Exposure Assessment of Carbendazim”

ImproRisk Scientific Report

Author: Dimitris Kafouris

Report Date: Dec 19, 2022 - 06:55:43 UTC

Table of Contents

1	Summary.....	3
2	Introduction	4
2.1	Background.....	4
2.2	Terms of Reference.....	4
3	Data and Methodology	4
3.1	Occurrence data	4
3.2	Consumption data	18
3.3	Food classification.....	20
3.4	Methodologies	20
4	Dietary Exposure Assessment.....	21
4.1	Distribution of exposure.....	22
4.2	Mean Exposure at the MB by Gender.....	23
4.3	Mean Exposure at the MB by Area.....	24
4.4	Mean Exposure at the MB by Population Class.....	25
4.5	Mean Exposure at the MB scenario by <i>[insert the demographics]</i>	26
4.6	Contributions of different food groups to the dietary exposure.....	27
5	Uncertainties.....	30
6	Conclusions.....	31
7	References.....	31
8	Abbreviations.....	32
9	Appendices.....	32

1 Summary

Carbendazim is the ISO common name for methyl benzimidazol-2-ylcarbamate (IUPAC). Its uses comprise of outdoor foliar spraying against fungi in cereals, sugar beet, fodder beet, oilseed rape and maize.

In the current report the dietary exposure of the target population is studied using ImproRisk model v.0.3.2. The aim of this risk assessment study was to estimate the chronic dietary Carbendazim intake of the population in Cyprus, to compare this exposure estimate with the Acceptable Daily Intake (ADI) of 20 µg/kg body weight (b.w.) per week and to calculate the contribution rate of the major food groups to the dietary Carbendazim exposure.

Mean and 95th percentile exposure for the Middle-bound scenario were calculated as 0.067 and 0.172 µg/kg b.w. per day. It was found that in all three scenarios (LB, MB, UB) the whole population was exposed much lower than the ADI value of 20 µg/Kg b.w. per day. The exposure of all population classes was much lower (up to 100 times) than the ADI for Carbendazim intake. Toddlers and infants had higher exposure than the other population classes due to their lower body weight. There was no significant difference in Carbendazim intake between genders and geographical areas.

In general fruits and some vegetables were the main contributors to the total Carbendazim exposure. It was also observed that Carbendazim was mostly found and with higher concentration in grape leaves, grapes, wine and fruits. Potatoes (9%), Tomatoes (7.2%), Red wine (6.8%), Apples (6.0%), pears (4.2%), followed by peaches, cucumbers, apricots and olive oil (3.7-3.9%) were the food categories with the highest contribution to the Carbendazim intake.

2 Introduction

Carbendazim is a widely used, systemic, broad-spectrum benzimidazole fungicide and a metabolite of benomyl. It is also employed as a casting worm control agent in amenity turf situations such as golf greens, tennis courts etc. and in some countries is licensed for that use only. The fungicide is used to control plant diseases in cereals and fruits, including citrus, bananas, strawberries, pineapples, and pomes. It is also controversially used in Queensland, Australia on macadamia plantations. A 4.7% solution of carbendazim hydrochloride, sold as Eertavas, is marketed as a treatment for Dutch elm disease. Studies have found high doses of carbendazim cause infertility and destroy the testicles of laboratory animals.

Maximum pesticide residue limits (MRLs) have reduced since discovering its harmful effects. The MRLs for fresh produce in the EU are now between 0.1 and 0.7 mg/kg with the exception of loquat, which is 2 mg/kg. The limits for more commonly consumed citrus and pome fruits are between 0.1 and 0.2 mg/kg.

Carbendazim is not acutely toxic via the oral, dermal and inhalation routes. It is not a skin or eye irritant but is a skin sensitizer. There is no indication of any direct neurotoxic potential of carbendazim. The overall acceptable daily intake (ADI), acceptable operator exposure level (AOEL) and acute reference dose (ARfD) of 0.02 mg/kg bw/day were based on the developmental data in rats and rabbits (NOAEL of 10 mg/kg bw/day), and applying a safety factor of 500.

2.1 Background

2.2 Terms of Reference

The aim of this risk assessment study was to estimate the chronic dietary Carbendazim intake of the population in Cyprus, to compare this exposure estimate with the Acceptable Daily Intake (ADI) of 20 µg/kg body weight (b.w.) per week and to calculate the contribution rate of the major food groups to the dietary Carbendazim exposure.

3 Data and Methodology

3.1 Occurrence data

3.1.1 Data collection and validation

Carbendazim occurrence data in food were extracted from LIMS for the years 2014-2020, and are shown in Tables 3.1. Only plant origin food was selected to be used in the calculation of the exposure. For results below LOD, EFSA's assumption was applied. Occurrence results below the LOQ were set to zero for the Low-bound scenario, half the LOQ for the Middle-bound scenario and LOQ for the Upper-bound scenario. Dilution factors were applied in order to estimate concentrations for different coffee and cocoa beverages,

tea beverages and liquid children and infant milk. The aggregated occurrence dataset is: Carbendazim 2014-2020_Aggregated_Plant origin_Final.xlsx with occurrence estimates for 282 food items.

Table 3.1 shows the aggregated occurrence values used in the exposure assessment of Carbendazim

Table 3.1: Aggregated occurrence values for Carbendazim

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A03GG	Coffee, cocoa, tea and infusions	1	56		0.0033	0.0102	0.0172
A03GH	Ingredients for coffee, cocoa, tea, and herbal infusions	2	56		0.0033	0.0102	0.0172
A03GJ	Coffee ingredients	3	9		0.0000	0.0131	0.0261
A03HQ	Tea leaves derivatives and tea ingredients	3	45		0.0036	0.0095	0.0154
A03JB	Flowers used for herbal infusions	3	2		0.0125	0.0150	0.0175
A04KK	Teas leaves, dry and/or fermented, and similar	4	45		0.0036	0.0095	0.0154
A0C6A	Coffee ingredients (RPC derivatives)	4	1		0.0000	0.0100	0.0200
A0D9E	Chamomile and similar-	4	2		0.0125	0.0150	0.0175
A0D9J	Coffee beans and similar-	4	8		0.0000	0.0134	0.0269
A03GK	Coffee beans, green	5	3		0.0000	0.0108	0.0217
A03GQ	Instant coffee powder	5	1		0.0000	0.0100	0.0200
A03JC	Chamomile	5	2		0.0125	0.0150	0.0175
A011X	Legumes, nuts, oilseeds and spices	1	164		0.0008	0.0065	0.0123
A016S	Spices	2	22		0.0026	0.0109	0.0192
A01AY	Processed legumes, nuts, oilseeds and spices	2	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A04RG	Legumes	2	133		0.0005	0.0047	0.0089

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A04RH	Nuts, oilseeds and oilfruits	2	8		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A011Y	Legumes fresh seeds (beans, peas etc.)	3	27		0.0004	0.0048	0.0091
A012R	Pulses (dried legume seeds)	3	106		0.0006	0.0047	0.0089
A015F	Oilseeds	3	8		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A017X	Seed spices	3	10		0.0000	0.0065	0.0130
A019Z	Root and rhizome spices	3	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A01AK	Bud spices	3	2		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A01AZ	Canned or jarred legumes	3	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A011Z	Beans (fresh seeds without pods) and similar-	4	4		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A012G	Peas (without pods) and similar-	4	23		0.0005	0.0048	0.0090
A012S	Beans (dry) and similar-	4	72		0.0008	0.0047	0.0085
A01BC	Canned or jarred peas	4	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A0CGQ	Coriander seeds and similar-	4	1		0.0000	0.0100	0.0200
A0CGX	Ginger roots and similar-	4	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A0CHA	Capers buds and similar-	4	2		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A0CZA	Cumin seed and similar-	4	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A0CZF	Anise seed and similar-	4	8		0.0000	0.0063	0.0125
A0DBP	Sunflower seeds and similar-	4	1		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A0DBQ	Sesame seeds and similar-	4	7		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A0DCD	Peas (dry) and similar-	4	15		0.0000	0.0048	0.0097
A0DCE	Lentils (dry) and similar-	4	19		0.0000	0.0049	0.0097
A012A	Broad beans (without pods)	5	2		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A012J	Garden peas (without pods)	5	23		0.0005	0.0048	0.0090
A013H	Broad beans (dry)	5	7		0.0039	0.0060	0.0081
A013J	Garden peas (dry)	5	2		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A013M	Chickpeas (dry)	5	13		0.0000	0.0048	0.0096
A013N	Black eyed peas (dry)	5	18		0.0004	0.0050	0.0096
A013Q	Lentils (dry)	5	19		0.0000	0.0049	0.0097
A015K	Sesame seeds	5	7		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A015L	Sunflower seeds	5	1		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A017Y	Anise seed	5	8		0.0000	0.0063	0.0125
A018D	Coriander seed	5	1		0.0000	0.0100	0.0200
A018E	Cumin seed	5	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A01AB	Ginger roots	5	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A01AM	Capers buds	5	2		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A000J	Grains and grain-based products	1	218		0.0014	0.0057	0.0100
A000K	Cereals and cereal primary derivatives	2	209		0.0014	0.0057	0.0101
A00CV	Breakfast cereals	2	9		0.0000	0.0039	0.0078
A000L	Cereal grains (and cereal-like grains)	3	159		0.0019	0.0061	0.0103
A04KS	Cereal and cereal-like flours	3	45		0.0000	0.0046	0.0092
A04LK	Processed and mixed breakfast cereals	3	9		0.0000	0.0039	0.0078
A0BY1	Groats	3	5		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A000F	Oat and similar-	4	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A000S	Maize and similar-	4	4		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A000Y	Common millet and similar-	4	3		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A001C	Rice and similar-	4	126		0.0023	0.0064	0.0104
A001M	Wheat and similar-	4	19		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A002G	Buckwheat flour	4	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A002L	Barley flour	4	11		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A002Y	Oat flour	4	5		0.0000	0.0045	0.0090
A002Z	Oat groats	4	3		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A003J	Rye flour	4	7		0.0000	0.0029	0.0057
A003X	Wheat flour	4	21		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A004G	Bulgur	4	2		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A04KH	Buckwheat and other pseudo-cereals and similar-	4	3		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A04QY	Cereal flakes and similar	4	9		0.0000	0.0039	0.0078
A0D9Y	Barley and similar-	4	3		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A000A	Teff grain	5	3		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A000N	Buckwheat	5	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A000P	Barley grains	5	3		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A000R	Quinoa grain	5	2		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A001D	Rice grain	5	126		0.0023	0.0064	0.0104
A003M	Rye flour, wholemeal	5	7		0.0000	0.0029	0.0057
A004C	Wheat flour, durum	5	5		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A00DN	Processed oat-based flakes	5	5		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A00DY	Processed rye-based flakes	5	4		0.0000	0.0025	0.0050
A001E	Rice grain, brown	6	11		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A00FJ	Vegetables and vegetable products	1	633		0.0149	0.0190	0.0232
A00FL	Flowering brassica	2	19		0.0000	0.0049	0.0097
A00GX	Bulb vegetables	2	32		0.0000	0.0032	0.0064
A00HN	Fruiting vegetables	2	265		0.0008	0.0049	0.0091
A00KR	Leafy vegetables	2	148		0.0536	0.0576	0.0616
A00PB	Legumes with pod	2	40		0.0000	0.0039	0.0078
A00QF	Root and tuber vegetables (excluding starchy- and sugar-)	2	59		0.0000	0.0036	0.0073
A00RR	Stems/stalks eaten as vegetables	2	21		0.0008	0.0058	0.0108
A00VQ	Herbs and edible flowers	2	47		0.0275	0.0325	0.0375
A00ZA	Processed or preserved vegetables and similar	2	2		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A00FM	Broccoli and similar-	3	17		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A00FT	Head brassica	3	16		0.0000	0.0027	0.0053
A00HB	Onions and similar-	3	32		0.0000	0.0032	0.0064
A00HP	Solanacea	3	165		0.0012	0.0056	0.0099
A00JK	Cucurbits fruiting vegetables	3	100		0.0000	0.0038	0.0077
A00KS	Lettuces and salad plants	3	55		0.0005	0.0052	0.0098
A00MG	Spinach-type leaves	3	50		0.0000	0.0040	0.0081
A00PC	Beans (with pods) and similar-	3	40		0.0000	0.0039	0.0078
A04MA	Aromatic herbs	3	47		0.0275	0.0325	0.0375
A04MB	Processed tomato products	3	2		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A0DEN	Globe artichokes and similar-	3	7		0.0000	0.0043	0.0086

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A0DEQ	Celeries and similar-	3	14		0.0012	0.0066	0.0119
A0DJQ	Grape leaves and similar species	3	27		0.2929	0.2963	0.2996
A0DLL	Cauliflowers and similar-	3	2		0.0000	0.0037	0.0075
A0DPB	Carrots and similar-	3	59		0.0000	0.0036	0.0073
A00FN	Broccoli	4	17		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A00FR	Cauliflowers	4	2		0.0000	0.0037	0.0075
A00FX	Head cabbages and similar-	4	16		0.0000	0.0027	0.0053
A00HC	Onions	4	32		0.0000	0.0032	0.0064
A00HQ	Tomatoes and similar-	4	84		0.0012	0.0057	0.0102
A00HZ	Peppers and similar-	4	51		0.0020	0.0061	0.0102
A00JC	Aubergines and similar-	4	23		0.0000	0.0045	0.0089
A00JL	Cucurbits with edible peel	4	71		0.0000	0.0040	0.0080
A00KD	Cucurbits with inedible peel	4	29		0.0000	0.0034	0.0067
A00LM	Roman rocket and similar-	4	12		0.0000	0.0035	0.0071
A00MH	Spinaches and similar-	4	46		0.0000	0.0040	0.0079
A00NB	Grape leaves	4	27		0.2929	0.2963	0.2996
A00PH	Broad beans (with pods)	4	2		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A00QH	Carrots	4	59		0.0000	0.0036	0.0073
A00RS	Globe artichokes	4	7		0.0000	0.0043	0.0086
A00RY	Celeries	4	14		0.0012	0.0066	0.0119
A00ZE	Preserved concentrated tomatoes	4	2		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A04KB	Celery leaves and similar-	4	2		0.0000	0.0037	0.0075
A04KD	Thyme and similar-	4	2		0.0000	0.0100	0.0200

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A04KF	Tarragon and similar-	4	2		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A0DHX	Sage and similar-	4	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A0DHZ	Parsley and similar-	4	11		0.0019	0.0044	0.0069
A0DJT	Chards and similar-	4	4		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A0DLB	Lettuces and similar-	4	43		0.0007	0.0056	0.0106
A0DMC	Okra and similar-	4	7		0.0000	0.0043	0.0086
A0ESV	Basils and mints	4	29		0.0439	0.0496	0.0552
A00FY	Head cabbages	5	16		0.0000	0.0027	0.0053
A00JA	Sweet peppers	5	51		0.0020	0.0061	0.0102
A00JD	Aubergines	5	23		0.0000	0.0045	0.0089
A00JF	Okra	5	7		0.0000	0.0043	0.0086
A00JQ	Courgettes and similar-	5	23		0.0000	0.0034	0.0067
A00KE	Melons and similar-	5	14		0.0000	0.0036	0.0071
A00KX	Lettuces (generic)	5	42		0.0007	0.0057	0.0106
A00KZ	Crisp lettuces	5	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A00MJ	Spinaches	5	46		0.0000	0.0040	0.0079
A00VV	Basil	5	7		0.0000	0.0036	0.0071
A00XA	Celery leaves	5	1		0.0000	0.0025	0.0050
A00XF	Coriander leaves	5	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A00XR	Lemongrass	5	2		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A00XV	Oregano	5	2		0.0000	0.0100	0.0200
A00XZ	Mints	5	22		0.0578	0.0642	0.0705
A00YE	Parsley	5	11		0.0019	0.0044	0.0069
A00YH	Sage	5	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A00ZF	Tomato paste	5	2		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A0DLQ	Watermelons and similar-	5	15		0.0000	0.0032	0.0063
A0DMB	Cucumbers and similar-	5	48		0.0000	0.0043	0.0086
A0DMX	Tomatoes	5	84		0.0012	0.0057	0.0102
A00HY	Cherry tomatoes	6	9		0.0000	0.0039	0.0078
A00JM	Cucumbers	6	48		0.0000	0.0043	0.0086
A00JR	Courgettes	6	23		0.0000	0.0034	0.0067
A00KF	Melons	6	14		0.0000	0.0036	0.0071
A00KJ	Watermelons	6	15		0.0000	0.0032	0.0063
A00ZR	Starchy roots or tubers and products thereof, sugar plants	1	94		0.0000	0.0045	0.0090
A00ZS	Starchy roots and tubers	2	94		0.0000	0.0045	0.0090
A00ZY	Tropical root and tuber vegetables	3	7		0.0000	0.0064	0.0129
A0DPP	Potatoes and similar-	3	87		0.0000	0.0044	0.0087
A00ZT	Potatoes	4	87		0.0000	0.0044	0.0087
A04JX	Cassava roots and similar-	4	7		0.0000	0.0064	0.0129
A010B	Taros	5	7		0.0000	0.0064	0.0129
A01BS	Fruit and fruit products	1	506		0.0083	0.0120	0.0158
A01ML	Processed fruit products	2	5		0.0000	0.0040	0.0080
A04RK	Fruit used as fruit	2	501		0.0084	0.0121	0.0159
A01BT	Citrus fruits	3	129		0.0060	0.0098	0.0137
A01DG	Pome fruits	3	87		0.0118	0.0152	0.0186
A01DT	Berries and small fruits	3	124		0.0056	0.0094	0.0133
A01GE	Stone fruits	3	63		0.0228	0.0255	0.0281

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A01HE	Miscellaneous fruits with edible peel	3	15		0.0035	0.0089	0.0142
A01JS	Miscellaneous fruits with inedible peel, small	3	14		0.0000	0.0025	0.0050
A01LA	Miscellaneous fruits with inedible peel, large	3	69		0.0031	0.0078	0.0125
A01MA	Dried fruit	3	5		0.0000	0.0040	0.0080
A01BX	Lemons and similar-	4	25		0.0288	0.0311	0.0334
A01CB	Mandarins and similar-	4	24		0.0000	0.0035	0.0071
A01CP	Oranges and similar-	4	79		0.0006	0.0051	0.0097
A01CX	Grapefruits and similar-	4	1		0.0000	0.0025	0.0050
A01DH	Apples and similar-	4	41		0.0048	0.0082	0.0117
A01DN	Pears and similar-	4	42		0.0186	0.0222	0.0259
A01DV	Grapes and similar fruits	4	57		0.0108	0.0147	0.0185
A01DZ	Strawberries and similar-	4	63		0.0012	0.0050	0.0088
A01ED	Cane fruits	4	3		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A01GG	Cherries and similar-	4	19		0.0081	0.0120	0.0159
A01GL	Peaches and similar-	4	26		0.0207	0.0230	0.0253
A01GP	Plums and similar-	4	10		0.0077	0.0102	0.0127
A01HH	Table olives and similar-	4	8		0.0000	0.0088	0.0175
A01LN	Guavas and similar-	4	2		0.0105	0.0118	0.0130
A01MB	Dried prunes	4	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A01ME	Dried vine fruits (raisins etc.)	4	3		0.0000	0.0033	0.0067
A04JJ	Blueberries and similar-	4	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A04JS	Bananas and similar-	4	22		0.0000	0.0048	0.0095
A0DPV	Pineapples and similar-	4	3		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A0DQC	Granate apples and similar-	4	31		0.0061	0.0097	0.0133
A0DQE	Papayas and similar-	4	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A0DQF	Mangoes and similar-	4	5		0.0012	0.0127	0.0242
A0DQP	Avocados and similar-	4	5		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A0DRG	Kiwi fruits and similar-	4	14		0.0000	0.0025	0.0050
A0DRY	Figs and similar-	4	7		0.0076	0.0090	0.0104
A0DVX	Apricots and similar-	4	8		0.0836	0.0846	0.0855
A0DVY	Loquats and similar-	4	4		0.0120	0.0132	0.0145
A01BP	Table olives	5	8		0.0000	0.0088	0.0175
A01BY	Lemons	5	25		0.0288	0.0311	0.0334
A01CY	Grapefruits	5	1		0.0000	0.0025	0.0050
A01DJ	Apples	5	41		0.0048	0.0082	0.0117
A01DL	Loquats	5	4		0.0120	0.0132	0.0145
A01DP	Pears	5	40		0.0195	0.0232	0.0268
A01DQ	Nashi pears	5	2		0.0000	0.0037	0.0075
A01EA	Strawberries	5	63		0.0012	0.0050	0.0088
A01EN	Raspberries and similar-	5	2		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A01EY	Blueberries	5	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A01GF	Apricots	5	8		0.0836	0.0846	0.0855
A01GK	Cherries (sweet)	5	19		0.0081	0.0120	0.0159
A01GQ	Plums	5	10		0.0077	0.0102	0.0127
A01HG	Figs	5	7		0.0076	0.0090	0.0104
A01JT	Kiwi fruits (green, red, yellow)	5	14		0.0000	0.0025	0.0050
A01LB	Avocados	5	5		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A01LF	Mangoes	5	5		0.0012	0.0127	0.0242
A01LG	Papayas	5	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A01LH	Granate apples	5	31		0.0061	0.0097	0.0133
A01LP	Pineapples	5	3		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A0CGD	Guavas	5	2		0.0105	0.0118	0.0130
A0DTY	Blackberries and similar-	5	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A0DVE	Table grapes and similar-	5	57		0.0108	0.0147	0.0185
A0DZB	Oranges	5	79		0.0006	0.0051	0.0097
A01DX	Table grapes	6	57		0.0108	0.0147	0.0185
A01EE	Blackberries	6	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A01EP	Raspberries (red and yellow)	6	2		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A032F	Sugar and similar, confectionery and water-based sweet desserts	1	23		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A04PA	Sugar and other sweetening ingredients (excluding intensive sweeteners)	2	23		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A033J	Honey	3	23		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A03PV	Food products for young population	1	56		0.0000	0.0035	0.0070
A03PY	Infant and follow-on formulae	2	32		0.0000	0.0033	0.0066
A03QX	Processed cereal-based food for infants and young children	2	13		0.0000	0.0048	0.0096
A03RC	Ready-to-eat meal for infants and young children	2	11		0.0000	0.0025	0.0050

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A03QZ	Cereals with an added high protein food which have to be reconstituted with water or other protein-free liquid	3	13		0.0000	0.0048	0.0096
A03RD	Ready-to-eat vegetable-based meal for children	3	1		0.0000	0.0025	0.0050
A03RJ	Ready-to-eat fruit-based meal for children	3	10		0.0000	0.0025	0.0050
A0EQL	Follow-on formulae	3	13		0.0000	0.0031	0.0062
A0EQM	Infant formulae	3	19		0.0000	0.0034	0.0068
A03PZ	Infant formulae, powder	4	19		0.0000	0.0034	0.0068
A03QK	Follow-on formulae, powder	4	13		0.0000	0.0031	0.0062
A039K	Fruit and vegetable juices and nectars (including concentrates)	1	20		0.0000	0.0082	0.0165
A03BM	Concentrated or dehydrated fruit/vegetables juices	2	2		0.0000	0.0188	0.0375
A0BX9	Fruit / vegetable juices and nectars	2	18		0.0000	0.0071	0.0142
A03BB	Fruit nectars (min. 25-50% fruit as defined in EU legislation)	3	3		0.0000	0.0117	0.0233
A0BY4	Fruit juices (100% from named source)	3	15		0.0000	0.0062	0.0123
A0ETV	Fruit/vegetable juice concentrate	3	2		0.0000	0.0188	0.0375
A039T	Juice, cranberry	4	1		0.0000	0.0025	0.0050
A03AF	Juice, pineapple	4	1		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A03AM	Juice, orange	4	13		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A03BF	Nectar, mango	4	1		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A03BG	Nectar, orange	4	2		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A03BN	Fruit juice concentrates	4	2		0.0000	0.0188	0.0375
A03CA	Juice concentrate, orange	5	2		0.0000	0.0188	0.0375
A03LZ	Alcoholic beverages	1	17		0.0442	0.0454	0.0465
A03MS	Wine and wine-like drinks	2	17		0.0442	0.0454	0.0465
A03MT	Wine	3	17		0.0442	0.0454	0.0465
A03MV	Wine, white	4	8		0.0312	0.0325	0.0338
A03MX	Wine, red	4	9		0.0557	0.0568	0.0579
A036M	Animal and vegetable fats and oils and primary derivatives thereof	1	10		0.0000	0.0100	0.0200
A0F3D	Animal and vegetable fats/oils	2	10		0.0000	0.0100	0.0200
A036N	Vegetable fats and oils, edible	3	10		0.0000	0.0100	0.0200
A036P	Olive oils	4	10		0.0000	0.0100	0.0200
A036Q	Olive oil, virgin or extra-virgin	5	10		0.0000	0.0100	0.0200
A03KE	Instant coffee (beverage)	4	21		0.0000	0.0002	0.0003
A03KK	Iced coffee	4	12		0.0000	0.0007	0.0015
A03KG	Coffee with milk or cream	4	12		0.0000	0.0007	0.0015
A03KB	Coffee espresso (beverage)	4	15		0.0000	0.0019	0.0038
A03KH	Coffee drink, cappuccino	5	21		0.0000	0.0007	0.0015
A03KA	Coffee beverages	3	35		0.0000	0.0007	0.0015
A03KD	Coffee (weak strength) beverage	4	11		0.0000	0.0007	0.0015
A03KF	Coffee beverage decaffeinated	4	11		0.0000	0.0007	0.0015
A03QF	Infant formula, milk-based, liquid	5	12		0.0000	0.0004	0.0008

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A03QR	Follow-on formula, milk-based, liquid	5	12		0.0000	0.0004	0.0008
A03LB	Tea beverages	3	12		0.0000	0.0001	0.0002
A03LG	Herbal and other non-tea infusions	3	12		0.0000	0.0001	0.0002
A03KY	Cocoa beverages	3	22		0.0001	0.0002	0.0003

3.2 Consumption data

Food consumption data were obtained from the EUMenu project funded by EFSA and the dietary survey was carried out in the years 2014-2018. The consumption data was the result of a survey of 1661 participants (male and female). The survey covered all five cities of Cyprus, rural and urban regions, and also all days of the week and the four seasons. The population classes and the number of participants in each class were: [a] infants: 3-11 months (269), [b] toddlers: 12-35 months (279), [c] other children: 3-9 years (300), [d] adolescents: 10-17 years (274), [e] adults: 18-64 years (275) and [f] elderly: 65-74 years (264). The consumption dataset is: Consumption data_CY population.xlsx with 82921 occasions.

Table 3.2: Food consumption survey details

Country	Start Year	End Year	Survey Code	Method of Survey	EU Menu Population	Survey Name	Survey Reference publication
CYPRUS	2014	2018		24h recall	1661	EU-Menu	

3.2.1 Target population

Figure 3.1 shows the number of subjects per population class and categorization between the two genders.

Figure 3.1: Number of subjects in the survey

3.2.2 Weight coefficients to adjust the sample for non – representativeness within the population

Table 3.3: Weight coefficients used

Gender	Population class	Weight coefficient	Number of subjects
FEMALE	Adolescents	265	137
FEMALE	Adults	2,044	139
FEMALE	Elderly	303	129
FEMALE	Infants	32	134
FEMALE	Other children	226	145
FEMALE	Toddlers	66	137
MALE	Adolescents	281	134
MALE	Adults	1,993	134
MALE	Elderly	277	130
MALE	Infants	36	134
MALE	Other children	229	151
MALE	Toddlers	70	137

3.3 Food classification

Consumption and occurrence data were both codified according to the FoodEx2 classification system developed by EFSA. At the moment of the generation of the present report the MTX catalogue version 13.1 was applied.

3.4 Methodologies

3.4.1 Chronic dietary exposure

Dietary exposure was assessed at individual level by multiplying the average daily consumption of each food with the corresponding mean occurrence estimated for Carbendazim summing up the respective intakes throughout the diet and finally dividing the results by the individual's body weight.

3.4.2 Dietary exposure assessment model

Dietary exposure assessment was performed using ImproRisk model version 0.3.2

4 Dietary Exposure Assessment

Table 4.1 presents the substance information.

Table 4.1: Substance information

key	
Chemical Substance	Carbendazim
Substance Category	Pesticide
Reference value	20 µg/Kg b.w. per day
Type of reference value	Acceptable Daily Intake (ADI)

Table 4.2 presents the exposure statistics.

Table 4.2: Summary exposure statistics of Carbendazim

Scenario			
key	LB (µg/Kg b.w. per day)	MB (µg/Kg b.w. per day)	UB (µg/Kg b.w. per day)
Min	0	0	0
Max	0.443	0.648	1.226
Mean	0.023	0.067	0.112
SD	0.04	0.059	0.089
P25	0.002	0.033	0.059
Median	0.008	0.054	0.092
P75	0.026	0.08	0.135
P95	0.094	0.172	0.281
pctOver	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%

* pctOver:Percentage of population above the reference value

Mean and 95th percentile exposure for the Middle-bound scenario were calculated as 0.067 and 0.172 µg/kg b.w. per day (Table 4.2). It was found that in all three scenarios (LB, MB, UB) the whole population was exposed much lower than the ADI value of 20 µg/Kg b.w. per day, as also shown in Figures 4.1 and 4.2.

4.1 Distribution of exposure

Probability distribution

Figure 4.1 shows the probability distribution of the exposure.

Figure 4.1: Probability distribution of exposure at the MB scenario

Cumulative distribution

Figure 4.2 shows the cumulative distribution of exposure.

Figure 4.2: Cumulative distribution of exposure at the MB scenario

4.2 Mean Exposure at the MB by Gender

Table 4.3: Summary exposure statistics Gender at MB scenario.

Gender	Min	Max	Mean	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	pctOver
FEMALE	0	0.613	0.068	0.062	0.031	0.052	0.078	0.187	0%
MALE	0	0.648	0.067	0.056	0.033	0.056	0.080	0.155	0%

Table 4.3 and Figure 4.3 shows that there is no significant difference between the two genders meaning same food consumption habits for male and female subjects.

Figure 4.3: Mean Exposure by Gender at MB scenario.

4.3 Mean Exposure at the MB by Area

Table 4.4: Summary exposure statistics by Area at MB scenario.

Area	Min	Max	Mean	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	pctOver
Ammochostos	0	0.537	0.069	0.066	0.033	0.048	0.080	0.250	0%
Larnaka	0	0.648	0.062	0.060	0.027	0.045	0.069	0.194	0%
Lefkosia	0	0.613	0.071	0.061	0.033	0.054	0.093	0.172	0%
Lemesos	0	0.529	0.069	0.060	0.038	0.056	0.080	0.171	0%
Pafos	0	0.458	0.065	0.045	0.032	0.055	0.078	0.149	0%

Figure 4.4: Mean Exposure by Area at MB scenario.

4.4 Mean Exposure at the MB by Population Class

The table

Table 4.5: Summary exposure statistics by Population Class at MB scenario.

Population class	Min	Max	Mean	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	pctOver
Adolescents	0.000	0.365	0.062	0.044	0.034	0.050	0.076	0.144	0%
Adults	0.002	0.425	0.057	0.046	0.030	0.047	0.070	0.134	0%
Elderly	0.007	0.405	0.066	0.053	0.031	0.052	0.078	0.161	0%
Infants	0.000	0.613	0.190	0.149	0.065	0.172	0.299	0.475	0%
Other children	0.011	0.572	0.107	0.071	0.062	0.087	0.130	0.244	0%
Toddlers	0.040	0.648	0.189	0.097	0.122	0.165	0.235	0.384	0%

In Table 4.5 and Figure 4.5 the exposure of each population class is shown. It was found that toddlers and infants had 2 or 3 times higher exposure than the other population classes. The lower body weight of these population classes is the main reason for the higher exposure. Also in all population classes the exposure is much lower (up to 100 times) than the ADI for Carbendazim intake.

Figure 4.5: Mean Exposure by Population Class at MB scenario.

4.5 Mean Exposure at the MB scenario by [Area and Population class]

Figure 4.6 illustrates the mean exposure to Carbendazim by population class and geographical area. It was found that there is no significant difference between the geographical areas in all population classes. The exposure seems to be independent of the geographical area. This is because the population in Cyprus has the same food consumption habits and the foodstuffs that are contaminated by Carbendazim are consumed by all population classes.

Figure 4.6: Cross Plot

4.6 Contributions of different food groups to the dietary exposure

The contribution of each main food group to the total Carbendazim exposure is shown in Figure 4.7. Potatoes (9%), Tomatoes (7.2%), Red wine (6.8%), Apples (6.0%), pears (4.2%), followed by peaches, cucumbers, apricots and olive oil (3.7-3.9%) were the food categories with the highest contribution to the Carbendazim intake. In general fruits and some vegetables were the main contributors to the total Carbendazim exposure. Carbendazim was most commonly found and with higher concentration in grape leaves, grapes, wine and fruits. Although, fruits were the most contaminated with Carbendazim, tomatoes, cucumbers and potatoes, with lower contamination appeared in the main contributors due to their high consumption by the whole population.

Figure 4.7 shows the contribution of food items at FoodEx Level 4

Figure 4.7: Contribution to the Carbendazim Total Exposure MB.

Table 4.6: Contribution to the Carbendazim Total Exposure (MB). Food items at FoodEx2 Level 4 with greater than 1% contribution

Level1	Level2	Level3	Level4	Contribution
Grains and grain-based products	Cereals and cereal primary derivatives	Cereal grains (and cereal-like grains)	Rice and similar-	1.25%
Grains and grain-based products	Cereals and cereal primary derivatives	Cereal and cereal-like flours	Wheat flour	1.08%
Grains and grain-based products	Breakfast cereals	Processed and mixed breakfast cereals	Cereal flakes and similar	1.19%
Vegetables and vegetable products	Bulb vegetables	Onions and similar-	Onions	1.39%
Vegetables and vegetable products	Fruiting vegetables	Solanacea	Tomatoes and similar-	7.18%
Vegetables and vegetable products	Fruiting vegetables	Cucurbits fruiting vegetables	Cucurbits with edible peel	3.81%
Vegetables and vegetable products	Fruiting vegetables	Cucurbits fruiting vegetables	Cucurbits with inedible peel	1.96%
Vegetables and vegetable products	Leafy vegetables	Grape leaves and similar species	Grape leaves	1.91%
Vegetables and vegetable products	Herbs and edible flowers	Aromatic herbs	Basils and mints	1.20%
Starchy roots or tubers and products thereof, sugar plants	Starchy roots and tubers	Potatoes and similar-	Potatoes	9.03%
Fruit and fruit products	Fruit used as fruit	Citrus fruits	Oranges and similar-	1.18%
Fruit and fruit products	Fruit used as fruit	Pome fruits	Apples and similar-	6.02%
Fruit and fruit products	Fruit used as fruit	Pome fruits	Pears and similar-	4.18%
Fruit and fruit products	Fruit used as fruit	Berries and small fruits	Grapes and similar fruits	1.68%
Fruit and fruit products	Fruit used as fruit	Stone fruits	Peaches and similar-	3.86%

Level1	Level2	Level3	Level4	Contribution
Fruit and fruit products	Fruit used as fruit	Stone fruits	Apricots and similar-	3.79%
Fruit and fruit products	Fruit used as fruit	Miscellaneous fruits with inedible peel, large	Bananas and similar-	3.34%
Animal and vegetable fats and oils and primary derivatives thereof	Animal and vegetable fats/oils	Vegetable fats and oils, edible	Olive oils	3.74%
Animal and vegetable fats and oils and primary derivatives thereof	Animal and vegetable fats/oils	Vegetable fats and oils, edible	Seed oils	1.03%
Fruit and vegetable juices and nectars (including concentrates)	Fruit / vegetable juices and nectars	Vegetable juices	Juice, tomato	1.54%
Fruit and vegetable juices and nectars (including concentrates)	Fruit / vegetable juices and nectars	Fruit juices (100% from named source)	Juice, orange	3.15%
Alcoholic beverages	Wine and wine-like drinks	Wine	Wine, red	6.79%
Food products for young population	Processed cereal-based food for infants and young children	Cereals with an added high protein food reconstituted	Cereals with an added high protein food reconstituted	1.40%

5 Uncertainties

The evaluation of the uncertainties in the exposure assessment of Carbendazim has been performed following the guidance of the Opinion of the Scientific Committee related to Uncertainties in Dietary Exposure Assessment. Table 5.1 presents a summary of uncertainties, highlighting the main sources of uncertainty and providing an estimate whether each source of uncertainty is likely to lead to an over- or under-estimation of the calculated dietary exposure.

Table 5.1: Summary of qualitative evaluation of the impact of uncertainties on the dietary exposure to Carbendazim.

Sources of uncertainty	Direction ¹
Different time frame between concentration data and consumption data	+/-
Long-term (chronic) exposure assessed from few days of consumption	+
Measurement error in amounts of food consumed	+/-
Measurement error in individual body weights	+/-
Assumptions taken into account for the preparation of occurrence data	+/-
Application of the substitution method on the preparation of occurrence data with high percentage of left-censored data	+
Level up approach matching in the FoodEx2 exposure hierarchy for the calculation of the exposure	+

¹ + = uncertainty with potential to cause over-estimation of exposure; - = uncertainty with potential to cause under-estimation of exposure

A number of uncertainties can be identified regarding the selection of parameters, such as Carbendazim concentration levels in foodstuffs and consumption data.

The uncertainty related to the representativeness of the occurrence data for certain food commodities with respect to the number of samples is taken into account. Given the fact that the analytical results were generated with an LC-MS/MS method in an accredited laboratory, this adds only slightly to the uncertainty of the analytical results.

Some potentially important extrapolation uncertainties arise since an individual survey of food consumption is used to estimate dietary exposure over a timescale longer than the survey duration. Remaining uncertainties relate to the measurement error in amounts of consumed foodstuffs and individual body weights.

In ImproRisk occurrence and consumption data matching for the calculation of the exposure is performed based on a level up approach matching in the FoodEx2 exposure hierarchy, which may lead to overestimation of the exposure.

Furthermore, several assumption taken into account in the preparation of the occurrence data (data from EFSA, dilution factors, aggregation) may lead to some uncertainties.

6 Conclusions

Mean and 95th percentile exposure for the Middle-bound scenario were calculated as 0.067 and 0.172 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ b.w. per day. It was found that in all three scenarios (LB, MB, UB) the whole population was exposed much lower than the ADI value of 20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{Kg}$ b.w. per day. The exposure of all population classes was much lower (up to 100 times) than the ADI for Carbendazim intake. Toddlers and infants had higher exposure than the other population classes due to their lower body weight.

There was no significant difference in Carbendazim intake between genders and geographical areas.

In general fruits and some vegetables were the main contributors to the total Carbendazim exposure. It was also observed that Carbendazim was mostly found and with higher concentration in grape leaves, grapes, wine and fruits. Potatoes (9%), Tomatoes (7.2%), Red wine (6.8%), Apples (6.0%), pears (4.2%), followed by peaches, cucumbers, apricots and olive oil (3.7-3.9%) were the food categories with the highest contribution to the Carbendazim intake.

7 References

1. EFSA. 2011b. Evaluation of the FoodEx, the food classification system applied to the development of the EFSA Comprehensive European Food Consumption Database. EFSA Journal 2011; 9(3):1970. [27 pp.] doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2011.1970.
2. Reasoned opinion on the toxicological properties and maximum residue levels (MRLs) for the benzimidazole substances carbendazim and thiophanate-methyl. EFSA Journal 2021;19(7):6773. doi: 10.2903/j.efsa.2021.6773.
3. Conclusion on the peer review of the pesticide risk assessment of the active substance carbendazim. EFSA Journal 2010; 8(5):1598. [76 pp.]. doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2010.1598.
4. EFSA (European Food Safety Authority), 2006. Guidance of the Scientific Committee on a request from EFSA related to Uncertainties in Dietary Exposure Assessment. The EFSA Journal. 438, 1-54.
5. EFSA. 2018. Internal report on the harmonisation of dilution factors to be used in the assessment of dietary exposure.

8 Abbreviations

Table 8.1: Abbreviations

Key	Description
BMDL	Benchmark dose lower limit (lower bound of benchmark dose interval)
b.w.	Body weight
LB	Lower bound
LOD	Limit of detection
MB	Middle bound
MoE	Margin of exposure
SD	Standard deviation
P25	25th percentile
P75	75th percentile
P95	95th percentile
UB	Upper bound
wcoeff	Weight coefficient

9 Appendices